

IDENTIFYING THE IMPACT OF SOME FACTORS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF THE MANAGEMENT OF ERASMUS MOBILITY PROJECTS IN HEIs

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper aims to determine the impact of some factors on the performance of the management of Erasmus mobility projects in higher education institutions.*

Methodology/approach – *There were processed a number of 427 responses obtained through questionnaires, from participants in Erasmus mobility projects, students and academic staff from Romania and abroad. The quality of responses was tested by applying Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and a factorial analysis was applied by using the principal components analysis algorithm, to group items and determine latent variables. Indicators such as, the percentage of the initial information, KMO statistics, the information retained by each item and the association coefficients, values, allowed the application of binary logistic regression.*

Findings – *Determining the factors that have a direct influence on the performance of management of Erasmus programme.*

Research limitations/implications – *Erasmus mobility projects are an important factor of internationalization in HEIs.*

Practical implications – *The findings of the paper have practical applicability in improving the management of Erasmus programme in HEIs.*

Originality/value – *Due to the pandemic situation Erasmus programme was affected by the decrease of the number of Erasmus+ mobility projects. The results of the paper may constitute reference points for HEIs in reinvigorating the programme.*

Key words: *Erasmus, Performance, Management*

Introduction

Taking into consideration that the purpose of the paper is to establish the factors that determine an improvement of the performance of the management of Erasmus mobility projects in higher education institutions, we carried out a quantitative research, based on questionnaires by using Likert scale (University of Newcastle Library, 2020). Through the SPSS Statistics program, we were able to process a number of 427 responses from Erasmus mobility participants, students, teachers and administrative staff from educational institutions, from Romania and from abroad.

In Table 1 one can see the studied variables.

Statistical validation of data

Considering that the data were achieved through the application of questionnaires with Likert measurement scale ("Statistics How To", 2022), before performing any analysis and creating latent variables, we have checked the liability of responses by using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (Dugard, Todman, & Staines, 2010 and Koning & Franses, 2003).

By applying this coefficient, we have determined therefore the quality of the answers, respectively the degree of confidence of the results collected from the questionnaires (Brown, 2002).

Table 1. Studied variables

Studied variables	Name of the variables
Q5	How would you rate the level of promotion and information activities carried out by your home university/institution regarding the Erasmus programme?
Q6	How would you assess the quality and professionalism of the Erasmus selection competition organized by home university/institution?
Q7	How would you rate the level of professionalism and transparency regarding the nomination process at home university/institution to the partner university/institution after being selected for an Erasmus mobility?
Q8	How would you appreciate the way in which your home university/institution supported you in filling in the Erasmus documents required for the success of the mobility in the host country?
Q9	How would you evaluate the level of support received from home university/institution during the whole application process at the host university/institution where selected to carry out Erasmus mobility?
Q10	How would you assess the information and support provided by your home university/institution during your mobility at the host university/institution?
Q11	How would you rate the support provided by home university/institution regarding the administrative part after returning from mobility?
Q13.1	The way the information regarding the Erasmus programme is disseminated at home university/institution
Q13.2	The selection process of the Erasmus candidates at home university/institution
Q13.3	The nomination process of the Erasmus candidates to the host institution at home university/institution
Q13.4	The monitoring process of mobility projects at home university/institution
Q13.5	The communication process with home institution during the project mobility at the host institution at home/host institution
Q14	How would you assess the level of promptitude and reaction of the host university/institution in sending the application documents in order to get the invitation letter required for mobility?
Q15	How would you rate the level of involvement and support of the host university/institution before the start of mobility?
Q16	How would you assess the quality of the administrative procedure regarding the mobility upon arrival at the host university/institution?
Q17	How would you assess the level of support that the host university/institution has had in mobility?
Q18.1	The information provided before their arrival in the mobility at host university/institution
Q18.2	Organizing the welcoming activities (orientation week, meeting with coordinators, meeting with homologues etc.) at host university/institution
Q18.3	The administrative support the mobility (for example processing Erasmus documents: certificates of arrival and departure, learning agreement, teaching or training agreements etc.)
Q18.4	Communicating with academic coordinators
Q18.5	The manner in which the problems that students encounter during mobility are managed at host university/institution
Q19.1	Streamline the application procedures
Q19.2	A more open attitude of the staff who manages the programme
Q19.3	A better communication between partner universities
Q19.4	More online information
Q20.1	Increasing the number of staff in Erasmus offices
Q20.2	A better coordination between home and host institutions
Q20.3	Digitalization of procedures
Q20.4	Increasing the transparency of the programme
Q21.1	Erasmus offices
Q21.2	Erasmus coordinators
Q21.3	Academic staff
Q21.4	Administrative staff
Q22	How would you rate the quality of the management the Erasmus programme of the institutions you came in contact with?

In order for the data to be validated, it is recommended that the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient registers values higher than 0.7 on each group of the analyzed items. It can be seen in Table 2 that the coefficients we have obtained are $\alpha > 0.8$ and $\alpha > 0.9$ and they indicate that the quality of the responses to the questionnaires has an internal consistency going from "good" to "excellent" ("Statistics How To", 2022).

Table 2. The values of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

Synthetic variable (latent)	Name of latent variable	Number of items (questions)	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient
Q5-Q11	Evaluation of the management of Erasmus mobility projects at home university/institution	7	0.929
Q13	Points in which is necessary an improvement of the management of Erasmus programme at home university/institution	5	0.934
Q14-Q17	Evaluation of the management of Erasmus mobility projects at host university/institution	4	0.897
Q18	Points in which is necessary an improvement of the management of Erasmus programme at host university/institution	5	0.960
Q19	Aspects which may improve the development of Erasmus mobility projects	4	0.881
Q20	Directions of improving the management of the Erasmus mobility programme	4	0.807
Q21	The importance of the role that Erasmus responsible play in the management of the programme	4	0.845

Taking into consideration the quality of the results achieved on each group of items, we can continue with the factorial analysis of the data by applying principal component analyses in order to create latent variables as linear combinations of initial items.

Principal component analyses

Principal Component Analysis (ACP) is also called the "Hotelling transformation or Karhunen-Loeve transformation" and is considered the "simplest analysis of eigenvectors". This analysis aims to reduce the number of variables used initially and to take into account a small number of variables that are considered representative. This analysis is "useful in reducing the number of dimensions" of the studied data and "the patterns can be identified without a significant loss of information" (Cărbureanu, 2010).

Following the principal component analyses, we obtained the data from Table 3.

For each group of items analyzed separately, we have created a latent variable as a linear combination of items. The connection between the items and the latent variable is given with the help of the coefficients that link the items to the latent variable, also called important coefficients (Table 3).

The following indicators have been used in order to analyze the quality of the latent variables created:

- The percentage of the initial information shows us how much of the initial information brought by the items is found in the latent variable (maximum value is 100%);
- KMO test measures the quality of the association between items, which shows the global quality of the analysis, statistics which register values in the range of [0; 1];
- The information retained from each item on the latent variable, registers values of up to 100%;
- The coefficients of association between the items and the latent variable, which expresses the connection between the items and the created variable, the values being in the range of [0; 1].

Table 3. The results of the factor analyses

Synthetic variable (latent)	Percentage of initial information KMO p-value	Initial items	Information retained from the item on latent variable (%)	Coefficients of association between items and the latent variable	Coefficients which link items to latent variable (Importance coefficient)
Q5-Q11 Assessment of the management of Erasmus mobility projects at home university/institution	70,34% 0,904 p-value=0,000	Q5	59,1	0,769	0.131
		Q6	65,2	0,807	0.138
		Q7	66,5	0,815	0.139
		Q8	74,9	0,866	0.148
		Q9	81,4	0,902	0.154
		Q10	75,7	0,870	0.149
		Q11	69,6	0,834	0.142
Q13 Points in which is an improvement of the management of Erasmus programme at home university/institution is necessary	79,245% 0,858 p-value=0,000	Q13.1	71,1	0,843	0.190
		Q13.2	80,0	0,895	0.201
		Q13.3	83,9	0,916	0.206
		Q13.4	84,0	0,917	0.206
		Q13.5	77,1	0,878	0.198
Q14-17 Assessment of the management of Erasmus mobility projects at host university/institution	76,49% 0,799 p-value=0,000	Q14	68.7	0.829	0.237
		Q15	80.0	0.894	0.255
		Q16	80,4	0.897	0.256
		Q17	76.9	0.877	0.251
Q18 Points in which an improvement of the management of Erasmus programme at host university/institution is necessary	86.35% 0.902 p-value=0.000	Q18.1	79.6	0.892	0.193
		Q18.2	85.8	0.926	0.200
		Q18.3	89.7	0.947	0.202
		Q18.4	85.7	0.926	0.200
		Q18.5	91.0	0.954	0.206
Q19 Aspects which may improve the development of Erasmus mobility projects	73.81% 0.786 p-value=0.000	Q19.1	66.1	0.813	0.237
		Q19.2	78.5	0.886	0.258
		Q19.3	78.7	0.887	0.258
		Q19.4	72.0	0.848	0.247
Q20 Directions of improving the management of the Erasmus mobility programme	63.45% 0.781 p-value=0.000	Q20.1	52.8	0.727	0.228
		Q20.2	71.2	0.844	0.265
		Q20.3	60.7	0.779	0.245
		Q20.4	69.1	0.831	0.261
Q21 The importance of the role that Erasmus responsible play in the management of the programme	68.37% 0.732 p-value=0.000	Q21.1	65.9	0.812	0.246
		Q21.2	75.4	0.869	0.263
		Q21.3	66.3	0.814	0.246
		Q21.4	65.8	0.811	0.245

If we analyze the results in Table 3, we see that all latent variables resulted correspond qualitatively, ie $KMO > 0.7$, the minimum percentage of information retained is 63.45%, the association coefficients between items and latent variables are greater than 0.7.

Binary logistic regression

In order to determine the factors which, influence the performance of Erasmus mobility projects, we applied binary logistic regression. It estimates the probability of an occurring event (in this case, good management appreciation). It is also called logistic regression and is used to predict the relationship between predictors as independent variables and a predicted and dependent variable ("Binary Logistic Regression", 2022). In this case, the question Q22 "How do you assess the quality of the management

within the Erasmus program of the institutions you came in contact with?" is considered as a dependent variable X.

We have considered two states, respectively a quality evaluated by respondents as "poor", marked with 0 and a quality evaluated by respondents as "good", marked with 1, this being the observed event. Given the nature of the data of the analyzed variables (dependent and factorial), to explain the relationships between them, we applied binary logistic regression. Thus, we can say that binary logistic regression predicts the probability that an observation will fall into one of the two categories of a dichotomous dependent variable based on one or more independent variables that can be either continuous or categorical.

If the factor variables are categorical (states are expressed in words or they show periods) then it is necessary to encode their states and choose the reference category. Thus, for variable 14.1 the reference category is "more than three participations", for variable 14.2 it is "2014-2020", and for the target group the reference category is "students". The information on these codings is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Coding the states of independent categorical variables

		Frequency	Codes		
			(1)	(2)	(3)
14.1 Total number of participations in Erasmus mobility projects	One participation	159	1.000	.000	.000
	Two participations	77	.000	1.000	.000
	Three participations	39	.000	.000	1.000
	More than three participations	151	.000	.000	.000
Target group	Administrative staff	109	1.000	.000	
	Professors	86	.000	1.000	
	Students	231	.000	.000	
14.2 The time interval of the last mobility	2007-2014	17	.000		
	2014-2020	409	1.000		

For the continuous variables Q5_Q11, Q13, Q14_Q17, Q18, Q19, Q20, Q21 there is no need to establish the reference category as they are numeric variables.

If the estimated probability of an event occurring is greater than or equal to 0.5 then it classifies the event as taking place (for example, a person appreciates the quality of management as good). If the probability is less than 0.5, then it classifies the event as not being in the opposite category, ie the project management is considered weak (Hayes & Matthes, 2009). These probabilities are calculated taking into account the independent (factorial) variables in the model (Table 5.)

In table 5, we have the contribution of each independent variable to the model (coefficients B) and their statistical significance at different levels. The Wald test is used to determine the statistical significance for each of the independent variables. The statistical significance of the test can be found in the p-value column. Exp (B) show us the probability of an event occurring based on a one-unit change of the independent variable when all other independent variables are kept constant.

The representativeness of the model - which expresses the performance of management within the Erasmus program - is analyzed by using both Cox & Snell R Square and Nagelkerke R Square indicators (Table 6) which show how much the variation of the dependent variable can be explained by the model, respectively it varies between 31.5% and 57.4%. It is preferred to interpret Nagelkerke R Square because it is underlain to register values in the interval [0; 1].

In order to verify the fit of the model we have also used Hosmer-Lemeshow test (Table 7).

Table 5. Estimation of the coefficients of the factorial variables in the model

Factor variables (independent)	Coefficients B	Wald test	p-value	Exp(B)
Q5_Q11	0.187	0.814	0.367	1.206
Q13	-0.855***	8.811	0.003	0.425
Q14_Q17	1.957***	51.726	0.000	7.075
Q18	0.592*	3.562	0.059	1.808
Q19	-0.235	0.538	0.463	0.791
Q20	-0.046	0.020	0.887	0.955
Q21	0.674**	6.116	0.013	1.962
Number of participants Cat of ref- more than 3 participations		13.476	0.004	
- one participation	-0.908	2.523	0.112	0.403
- two participations	-2.173***	10.771	0.001	0.114
- three participations	-2.142***	7.087	0.008	0.117
Last mobility period	0.427	0.228	0.633	1.348
Target group Cat. of ref-students		3.405	0.182	
- administrative staff	0.243	0.180	0.671	1.275
- professors	1.317*	3.392	0.066	3.731
Constant	3.980	40.980	0.000	53.529

Significance of factors: *** with a significance level of 1%, ** with a significance level of 5% and * with a significance level of 10%.

Table 6. Representativeness of the model

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	177.826	0.315	0.574

Table 7. Testul Hosmer and Lemeshow

Step	Chi-square	df	p-value
1	5.956	8	0.652

The Hosmer-Lemeshow test is a statistical test for "goodness of fit" for logistic regression models. The test evaluates whether or not the observed events match the expected events in the subgroups of the model population. Thus, the null hypothesis is that there are no significant differences between the observed and the expected events, ie predicted by the model. As p-value = 0.652 > 0.05 it results that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, ie the model is good.

Another modality which confirms that the model is good, is the percentage of the correctly predicted cases, ie for all cases analyzed we have a very good percentage of 92.5%. For the prediction of the "weak" state we have a percentage of 58.6% of correct predictions, and for the "good" state a very good percentage of 97.8% (Table 8).

Table 8. Classification of results

Observed		Prediction		
		Q22		Percentage of correct predictions
		week	good	
Q22	week	34	24	58.6
	good	8	360	97.8
Total percentage				92.5

Findings

We performed a binary logistic regression to determine the effects of factor variables Q5_Q11, Q13, Q14_Q17, Q18, Q19, Q20, Q21, the number of participations in Erasmus programs, the period of the last mobility and the affiliation of a target group on the probability that participants appreciate as good the quality of the management of such projects.

The model was statistically significant, $\chi^2(8) = 5.956$, $p = 0.652$, (Table 7) the variation explained being 57.4%, (table 6), 92.5% of the cases are correctly classified (Table 8).

The variables Q14-Q17 have the greatest influence on the assessment of the performance of management, respectively:

- the level of promptness and reaction of the host university in sending the application documents which are necessary for the participants in order to obtain the letter of invitation;
- the support of the beneficiaries before the start of their mobility received from the host university;
- the administrative procedures carried out at the host university on the arrival of the beneficiaries in mobility;
- the support provided to the beneficiaries at the host university during the mobility.

According to table 5, professors have a 3.73 times higher probability - compared to students - to appreciate the quality of Erasmus management, and administrative staff appreciate similarly to students. The period of the last mobility does not influence the management's assessment ($p = 0.633$) (Table 5).

Participants in more than three mobility projects have a higher probability to appreciate the quality of Erasmus mobility projects than the ones participating in one or two mobility projects.

The role of the Erasmus responsible has a direct influence on the performance of the management of Erasmus programme.

Conclusions

It seems that the host university has an important role regarding the quality of the Erasmus programme, from the respondent's point of view. This could be explained by the fact that the support and feedback of the host university is more important as it has the "power" to accept or deny a mobility and on it also depends the quality of the mobility of participants during their staying at the host university.

The fact that professors appreciate more the quality of management within Erasmus, than students or administrative staff, could be due to the fact that they provide lectures at the host university and therefore they enjoy a different status.

Regarding the fact that the people who participate in more Erasmus mobility projects have a higher probability to appreciate the quality of Erasmus programme is of a great importance and is an encouragement for universities to increase the number of mobility projects which is also an important indicator of internationalization.

In what concerns the role of the Erasmus responsible is very useful to have the confirmation of their importance in the management of Erasmus programme, as this could lead to better administrative assistance, once acknowledged.

The results of the paper are important for the management of Erasmus programme in higher education institutions and can be considered an important tool for HEIs in order to improve the performance of the management of Erasmus programme, especially by taking into consideration also the pandemic situation which lead to decrease of the number of Erasmus mobility projects and to a confuse management.

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